

Observation of bulk states and spin-polarized topological surface states in transition metal dichalcogenide Dirac semimetal candidate NiTe₂

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We predict NiTe₂ to be a type-II Dirac semimetal based on *ab initio* calculations and explore its bulk and spin-polarized surface states using spin- and angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (spin-ARPES). Our results show that, unlike PtTe₂, PtSe₂, and PdTe₂, the Dirac node in NiTe₂ is located in close vicinity to the Fermi energy. Additionally, NiTe₂ also hosts a pair of band inversions below the Fermi level along the Γ -A high-symmetry direction, with one of them leading to a Dirac cone in the surface states. The bulk Dirac nodes and the ladder of band inversions in NiTe₂ support unique topological surface states with chiral spin texture over a wide range of energies. Our work paves the way for the exploitation of the low-energy type-II Dirac fermions in NiTe₂ in the fields of spintronics, infrared plasmonics, and ultrafast optoelectronics.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The discovery of topological semimetals has ushered in a new era of exploration of massless relativistic quasiparticles in crystalline solids [1–5]. These arise as emergent quasiparticles in crystals with linearly dispersing bands in the vicinity of a degenerate band crossing point (either accidental or symmetry-enforced) and are protected by crystalline symmetries [6]. Double, triple, and quadruple degeneracy of the band crossing leads to topologically protected Weyl [7–15], triple point [16–22], and Dirac fermions [23–31], respectively. In contrast to their high energy counterparts, these emergent quasiparticles are not protected by Lorentz symmetry and can also occur in a tilted form, giving rise to type-I and type-II Dirac fermions. Specifically, Na₃Bi [27,30] and Cd₃As₂ [26,31] are type-I Dirac semimetals (DSMs), while the transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) PtTe₂ [32–34], PtSe₂ [35], and PdTe₂ [33,36,37] are type-II DSM.

In group X Pd- and Pt-based dichalcogenides, the bulk Dirac node lies deep below the Fermi level (~ 0.6 , ~ 0.8 , and ~ 1.2 eV in PdTe₂, PtTe₂, and PtSe₂, respectively) [32,33,36–37], hindering their successful exploitation in technology. In contrast, NiTe₂ is expected to host type-II Dirac fermions in the vicinity of the Fermi energy [38]. The so far performed experimental studies on NiTe₂ have primarily focused on its

crystal structure and transport properties while its topological band structure remains unexplored [38–45]. Motivated by this, we explored the electronic band structure of NiTe₂ by means of spin- and angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES) in combination with density functional theory (DFT).

Our *ab initio* calculations and ARPES data demonstrate the existence of a pair of type-II Dirac nodes in NiTe₂ along the C₃ rotation axis, lying just above the Fermi energy. Additionally, we show that NiTe₂ also hosts a series of inverted band gaps (IBG). Especially, one of the IBG below the Fermi level supports a Dirac cone in the surface states. Together, the bulk Dirac node and the pair of IBG in NiTe₂ give rise to topological spin-polarized surface states over a wide range of energies, which we explored using spin-resolved ARPES measurements. This nontrivial band morphology in NiTe₂ originates primarily from the 5*p*-orbital manifold of the Te atoms modified by the intralayer hybridization, trigonal crystal field splitting, and spin-orbit coupling.

II. STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATION AND METHODOLOGY

Bulk NiTe₂ crystallizes in the CdI₂ type trigonal structure (space group $P\bar{3}m1$, number 164). It has a layered structure with individual monolayer stacked together via weak van der Waals force. As shown in Figs. 1(a) and 1(b), each monolayer has three sublayers, with the central Ni layer being sandwiched between two adjacent Te layers (Ni-Te bond length 2.60 Å). The observation of sharp spots in the low-energy diffraction pattern (LEED) in Fig. 1(c) confirms

FIG. 1. (a) The side view and (b) hexagonal crystal structure of NiTe_2 with the C_3 rotation axis. Layers of Ni are stuffed between two Te layers. (c) The LEED pattern of (0001)-oriented NiTe_2 single crystals, acquired at a primary electron beam energy of 84 eV, clearly indicates its purity and the threefold symmetry along the (001) direction. (d) The bulk and the (001) surface Brillouin zone (BZ) of NiTe_2 .

the high quality of the NiTe_2 crystals cleaved along the (001) direction, along with the presence of threefold symmetry. Surface cleanliness of the as-cleaved samples was checked by high-resolution electron energy loss spectroscopy and x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. The details of crystal preparation and characterization, ARPES measurements, and DFT calculations are presented in Secs. S1, S2, and S3 of the Supplemental Material (SM) [46].

III. ELECTRONIC BAND STRUCTURE

The electronic band structure of NiTe_2 including spin-orbit coupling is shown in Fig. 2(a). It clearly depicts the presence of a pair of tilted band crossings along the Γ -A direction. The presence of inversion and time-reversal symmetry mandates these bands to be doubly degenerate. Furthermore, the Γ -A high-symmetry direction is the invariant subspace of the threefold rotation (C_3) symmetry, and a symmetry analysis reveals that the crossing bands have opposite rotation character. This prevents their hybridization, resulting in a pair of gapless quadruply degenerate type-II Dirac points. The type-II nature of the DSM phase is also confirmed by the fact that the Dirac point appears at the touching point of the electron and hole pocket, as highlighted in Fig. 2(b).

Our photon-energy dependent ARPES data, in part presented in Figs. 2(d) and 2(h), results in the k_z dispersion presented in Fig. 2(c). Our experimental results are consistent with the DFT-based bulk band structure calculations. Extrapolating the fitted DFT band structure, we find that the Dirac cone is located just above (~ 20 meV) the Fermi energy. Our attempt to electronically dope the sample via

alkali metal (potassium) deposition (see Fig. S6 in SM [46]), and shift the Fermi energy above the Dirac point, revealed that only the surface states in NiTe_2 are impacted by surface deposition. Bulk doping is needed to shift the bulk bands. Note that in the inset of Fig. 2(c), the photoemission measurement is unable to sufficiently resolve the lower velocity band of the Dirac node. The photoemission intensity is a product of the spectral function and the photoemission matrix elements. The low photoemission intensity of the low velocity band likely arises from the small value of the corresponding photoemission matrix element. Furthermore, the low resolution along the k_z direction is a well known shortcoming of ARPES [47].

Extended energy range ARPES spectra for the two high-symmetry directions are shown in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d). These spectra are mainly dominated by the surface states, as seen from the comparison with the calculated band structure in Figs. 3(e) and 3(f). In order to understand their origin, we note that there are two symmetry inequivalent Te atoms (Te^1 and Te^2) and a single Ni atom in a unit cell of NiTe_2 . The electronic configuration of Ni is $4s^2 3d^8$ and that of Te is $4d^{10} 5p^4$. We find that similar to other group-X TMDs [33,48], the Te $5p$ orbital manifold in NiTe_2 , aided by the interplay between intralayer hopping, crystal field splitting, and SOC strength, gives rise to most of the bulk Dirac nodes and multiple inverted band gaps. To highlight this, we show the evolution of the p -orbital manifold of the Te atoms in Fig. 3(a). To start with [step I in Fig. 3(a)], strong intralayer hybridization between the Te^1 and Te^2 p orbitals results in bonding and antibonding states. These orbitals are further split (in step II), due to a strong trigonal crystal field generated by the layered crystal structure of NiTe_2 , separating p_z from the p_x, p_y orbitals. Inclusion of SOC (step III) further splits the orbitals into $|J, |m_J||$ states. Step IV of Fig. 3(a) highlights the effect of the dispersion along the Γ -A direction and the formation of the bulk type-II Dirac point along with multiple band inversions in the valance band.

The irreducible representation of some of these states at the Γ and A points and along the Γ -A high-symmetry line is shown in Fig. 3(b). The bulk Dirac point originates from the crossing of the Δ_4 and $\Delta_{5,6}$ states along the Γ -A direction. As discussed earlier, the doubly degenerate Δ_4 and $\Delta_{5,6}$ bands have opposite rotation characters (+1 and -1, respectively) and, therefore, the Dirac point is protected from gap opening by any perturbation which respects the C_3 symmetry. Additionally, Fig. 3(b) also highlights the existence of a pair of IBGs in the valance band at the A point. However, in comparison to PdTe_2 , the parity of the crossing bands at the A point for NiTe_2 is different and only the lower IBG supports a Dirac node in the surface states. See Sec. S5 in the SM [46] for a more detailed discussion and comparison of the topological band structure and surface states with PdTe_2 .

The Dirac-like conical crossing in the surface states of NiTe_2 (at -1.4 eV) is evident in the ARPES data taken along the two high-symmetry directions $\bar{K}$ - Γ - $\bar{K}$ and $\bar{M}$ - Γ - $\bar{M}$ as shown in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d). The dominant surface bands are indicated by the red arrows. In addition to the Dirac cone, several other surface states are present in NiTe_2 , owing to several band inversions below and above the Fermi level. Along the $\bar{M}$ - Γ - $\bar{M}$ direction, the surface state near the Fermi

FIG. 2. (a) Band structure of NiTe₂ (including SOC) clearly showing the tilted type-II Dirac node along the Γ -A direction (at D). The irreducible representation of the bands (close to the Fermi energy) at the Γ and A points are also marked. (b) The Fermi surface of NiTe₂ originating from the crossing Dirac bands. The type-II Dirac points appear at the touching points of the electron and hole pockets. (c) The zoom of the band structure in the vicinity of the type-II Dirac point. The inset shows the experimental k_z dispersion along Γ -A deduced from the $h\nu$ -dependent data measured along the Γ - K direction [shown in part in (d)–(h)]. Note that the low velocity band of the Dirac node is not clearly resolved in our experiments (see text for details). (d)–(h) The measured band dispersion along the K - Γ - K direction for different k_z values, with the red dashed lines indicating the bulk DFT band structure. The blue arrows in panel (f) mark the surface states. Data were taken at photon energies of 17, 19, 21, 23, and 25 eV, respectively. Panel (f) corresponding to $k_z = 0.34 c^*$ is closest to the location of the Dirac point ($k_z = 0.35 c^*$ in our DFT calculations). Note that, for matching with the experimental data, we have shifted the DFT band structure downward by 100 meV.

energy has its origin from a band inversion above the Fermi energy (see Fig. 3(b), and Fig. S3 in SM [46]) and the corresponding surface Dirac cone lies above the Fermi level. While its Dirac-like nature is significantly altered far away from the Γ point, we demonstrate its topological origin by displaying its chiral spin texture in Fig. 4. Similar surface states have also been observed in other Te-based TMDs like PtTe₂ and PdTe₂, while they are absent in the Se based compounds like PtSe₂. This is a consequence of the avoided band inversion in PtSe₂ resulting from the reduced interlayer hopping [32,49].

IV. SPIN-POLARIZED SURFACE STATES

Since these surface states have a topological origin, we now focus on the spin polarization of the bands using spin-polarized ARPES. In Fig. 4(a) we display the spin-resolved data superimposed directly onto the spin-integrated band structure shown earlier in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d). The measured spin polarization matches reasonably well with the calculated spin textures reported in Figs. 4(b) and 4(g). In the present dataset, the spin component is always perpendicular to the dispersion direction. The most prominent feature in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) is the crossover of two opposite spin polarizations of almost equal magnitude for the surface state bands crossing at the Γ point at a binding energy of

~ -1.4 eV. This confirms the helical nature of the spin-momentum locking in the vicinity of the surface Dirac point, resulting from the IBG with the $Z_2 = 1$ topological order. In Figs. 4(c)–4(e), we display the spin-polarized spectra and the spin polarization for the points marked by black arrows in Fig. 4(a). The measured polarization perpendicular to Γ - K reaches almost 50%.

In the case of the bands along the $\bar{M}$ - $\bar{\Gamma}$ - $\bar{M}$ direction of the surface BZ [Figs. 4(f) and 4(g)], the polarization was measured for the electron-pocket-like surface states close to the Fermi energy. As discussed previously, although their shape is considerably different than usual topological surface states, the clear spin polarization demonstrates their topological origin (see Fig. S3 of SM [46]). These indeed appear to be the most prominent spin-polarized features also in the calculated spin polarization perpendicular to the $\bar{\Gamma}$ - $\bar{M}$ direction. The high values of the measured and calculated spin polarization indicates that NiTe₂ belongs to the recently identified topological-ladder family of Pt/PdTe₂ [33,48].

V. CONCLUSION

To summarize, we demonstrate NiTe₂ to be a type-II DSM using DFT-based *ab initio* calculations and explore its bulk and spin-polarized surface states using spin-resolved ARPES

FIG. 3. (a) The evolution of the Te 5p orbitals in the formation of Dirac-cone states in NiTe₂. Step (I) shows the creation of bonding and antibonding orbitals. Step (II) shows the effect of the strong trigonal crystal field which separates the p_z orbitals from the $p_{x,y}$ orbitals. In step (III), we show the splitting of these states into the $|J, |m_j||$ states in the presence of SOC. In step (IV), we demonstrate the effect of out of plane dispersion and the formation of the Dirac point. (b) The orbital-resolved band structure and various band inversions along the ΓA high-symmetry direction are shown along with the irreducible representations of the bands. In panels (c) and (d) we show the ARPES data (for $h\nu = 24$ eV) along $\bar{K}-\bar{\Gamma}-\bar{K}$ and $\bar{M}-\bar{\Gamma}-\bar{M}$ (for $h\nu = 30$ eV) directions of the (001) surface BZ, respectively. ARPES results are consistent with the DFT predictions in panels (e) and (f). To match the ARPES results with DFT, we have used a surface potential of -0.14 eV.

measurements. We show that, in contrast to a similar class of materials like PtTe₂, PdTe₂, and PtSe₂, where the Dirac point is buried deep in the valence band, the Dirac point in NiTe₂ is located in the vicinity of the Fermi energy. In addition to the bulk Dirac node, the Te p -orbital manifold in NiTe₂ also gives rise to a series of IBGs with nontrivial Z_2 topological

orders. Together, these give rise to topological Dirac nodes in the surface states characterized by the particular spin texture over a wide range of energies. Our findings establish NiTe₂ as a prime candidate for exploration of Dirac fermiology and applications in TMD-based spintronic devices, infrared plasmonics, and ultrafast optoelectronics.

FIG. 4. Measured and calculated spin texture for the bands along $\Gamma-\bar{K}$ (a),(b) and $\Gamma-\bar{M}$ (f),(g) in the BZ. Experiments were performed in the same conditions as in Fig. 3; (c)–(e) spin-polarized spectra and spin polarization for the points along $\bar{\Gamma}-\bar{K}$ marked by black arrows in (a); in all figures red/blue indicate positive/negative polarization perpendicular to the high-symmetry direction. E_{bin} denotes the binding energy.

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